

THE PAKISTAN-INDIA WATER DISPUTE IN THE ERA OF CLIMATE CHANGE: POLICY CHALLENGES AND WAY FORWARD

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ABSTRACT

The dispute over the Indus River Basin between Pakistan and India is becoming critical due to the pressures posed by climate change. This Paper discusses how melting glaciers, changing rainfall patterns, and rising temperatures are redefining water access and amplifying security risks in South Asia. It assesses the intersection of environmental stressors with geopolitical tensions in the Indus Basin using Environmental Security Theory. Key Findings indicate that existing Indus Water Treaty's (IWT) framework is straining as climate change is already reducing river flows and intensifying seasonal variability. Simultaneously, the competition for scarce water resources is increased due to socio-economic factors (agricultural water, population growth, and developmental projects). Under Climate stress, the shortcomings of IWT are firm provisions and its lack of flexibility for changing conditions. This study uses a qualitative, case-study approach based on secondary sources to analyze recent developments (e.g. hydro-project disputes, treaty challenges) and how they demonstrate broader water security issues. In conclusion, unless flexible cooperation is pursued, climate change acts as a "threat multiplier". This paper recommends improving basin wide data sharing and management, updating water sharing mechanisms, and incorporating climate projections into bilateral agreements to put off conflict and ensure sustainable water security.

Keywords

Climate Change, Environmental Security, Indus Waters Treaty (IWT), Water Scarcity

INTRODUCTION

Pakistan-India water relations are influenced by political, historical, and geographical factors on the one hand, and ecological factors on the other. According to Haines (2014), the 1947 partition and the establishment of the two independent dominion states of India and Pakistan from the erstwhile British India were the events that changed water relations. The people of both regions relied on the Indus basin for irrigation, and when Pakistan was created, the basin's flow was split between the two newly created states.

This split caused tensions right away because Pakistan is downstream and India is at the upper end of the basin, controlling the head waters (Molle, 2009). The long-running competition between nuclear nations, one of the most intense rivalries on the international scene is that between India and Pakistan, which might have disastrous consequences for South Asia and the surrounding area. Since the two nations gained their independence from the British Empire in 1947, they have engaged in four wars against one

another. The final one, the Kargil conflict in 1999, was fought in the shadow of nuclear weapons. There have been worries that we may be living in a period when another war breaks out, possibly including nuclear weapons. Pakistani and Indian rivalry over river resources has been a source of interstate conflict for more than 50 years (Wirsing & Jasparro, 2006). Control of Kashmir's land and cross-border terrorism has historically been major factors in escalating the India-Pakistan conflict. However, the expanding environmental catastrophe of the twenty-first century, which includes the effects of human-induced climate change, is making the contest much more intense. One of the most impacted areas by climate change is South Asia. Extreme and fluctuating precipitation patterns, water stress, droughts, flooding, sea level rise, and increased coastal cyclone activity are some of the subcontinent's climate threats. The "Indus watershed" was used to define the border lines when British India was divided into two states in 1947 (Gardner, 2019). Although the majority of irrigation systems are in Pakistan, a large portion of the headwaters are in India.

Many political geographers consider the 1960 Indus Waters Treaty (IWT) to be a pillar of water diplomacy between India and Pakistan. According to Menon (2015), the treaty is a unique instance of effective trans-boundary water cooperation that was supported by the World Bank and maintained despite the nations' enmity. Under the principle of equitable utilization, a notion derived from international water law, the treaty gave India the eastern rivers (Ravi, Beas, Sutlej) and Pakistan the western rivers (Indus, Jhelum, Chenab). Nearly 300 million people in India and Pakistan are fed by the Indus River, which has a catchment area of 1,120,000 square kilometers and is of major geographical, political, economic, and social relevance for both nations (Clift, 2002). Pakistan relies on the Indus River for approximately 90% of its crop production and for about 65% of its irrigation water (Mustafa, 2010). Wirsing & Jasparro (2007), highlighting the importance of water resources in South Asia said, the balance of power depends on water resource, meaning that water acts as a geopolitical factor in South Asia mainly between Pakistan and India. The framework of hydro-politics map is formed by the concept of India's upstream control, or regulating the flow of water into Pakistan. Aslam

(2022) suggests that this control can be utilized as a "soft power" political pressure tool.

Regarding the future, experts predict that both nations' capacity to work together on water sharing and climate change will be crucial to the region's ability to adapt to its effects. Haddeland et al. (2014) also made the case that models of water supply and demand, as well as the consequences for sharing water resources, should take climate change adaptation into account. For example, using water efficiently, improving water storage and infrastructure for long term water use. Joint reservoirs and irrigation system development that adapts to climate change, in collaboration with other nations, are likely options for water management (Link et al. 2016). In order to improve knowledge of water in relation to national security Liebenguth (2020) urges additional regional discussions that support sustainable water management.

Research Significance

Trans-boundary water management and climate security are the two vital issues that are bridged in this study. This study points towards the collaborative resilience building in a controversial region, and stresses that in the light of 21st century challenges; even a long eduring treaty (IWT) may need restructuring. This study aims to explore the shortcomings of IWT that pose probable conflict risks under climate stress, along with how climate change impacts water flow and availability in the Indus River Basin, and the effects of socio-economic drivers on water allocation. This study will help draw the attention of policy makers to take necessary measures in adressing the problem, which will help in avoiding a potential conflict.

LITERATURE REVIEW

How cooperation or coflict is driven by the shared water resources is long studied by the scholars of trans-boundary water. Scarcity of water more often promotes negotiation rather than an open war, as mutual dependence is recognized by the riparian states, is what the research of Aaron Wolf informs. However, when the downstream users are affected by the upstream actions (diversions, dams) without any agreement on mitigation is when diagreements occur. Nile, Jordan, and Euphrates are some classic cases where tensions have heightened due to lack of legal frameworks and

distrust. In South Asia, the Pakistan-India context is unique due to Kashmir conflict, water is often securitized and is seen as a strategic resource, and Indus is one of several trans-boundary basins (others in South Asia include the Ganges-Brahmaputra, the Mekong, etc.). Literature on environmental security observes that existing agreements will be put to test by climate induced variability. Wolf (2018) examined that problems likely to worsen with climate change, because, “many treaties do not account for greater variability in flow”. Certainly, the Indus Water Treaty itself is vulnerable to surprise events as it lacks explicit mechanism for river flow shifts or droughts.

The partition of the basin was formalized by the Indus Water Treaty (IWT) of 1960. It gave Pakistan nearly sole use of the western rivers (Indus, Jhelum, and Chenab) and to India it gave unrestricted use of the eastern rivers (Ravi, Beas, and Sutlej). Under strict design constraints, India retained limited rights on western rivers (for irrigation structures and power generation). For dispute resolution, the Permanent Indus Commission was also set up by the World Bank sponsored agreement. The IWT survived multiple wars, so many analysts call it as “one of the world’s most successful water treaties”. But, due to its rigidity and outdated framework, it is often criticized, as climate change, groundwater use, or future demand growth is originally not considered in the IWT. Recent study highlights that in treaty’s provisions, the climate impacts (glacial melt, extreme floods) were never anticipated. Banerji (2024) comments that under warming conditions, the risk of resource conflict is heightening, as Pakistan and India “continue to exploit the basin without considering the impact on the climate”.

The Indus is highly sensitive to climate change, is confirmed by a legitimate body of hydrological research. The basin’s headwaters lie in the Hindu Kush-Karakoram-Himalaya, home to about 60,000 glaciers. A large portion (over 40%) of Indus flow comes from snow and glaciers melt. Recent studies (Giese et al., 2022) show that the glacier melts contribution exceeds that of most other basins globally. Rising temperatures are already causing accelerated glacial retreat in parts of the basin (especially lower-altitude glaciers), which can paradoxically increase flows in the near term but threaten long-term supply. Indeed,

observations from 1962-2014 show a roughly 5% decline in Indus river flows, even before accounting for human withdrawals. Future projections under high emission scenarios are dire: climate models suggest 30-40% reductions in mean flows by 2050 or 2100. These reductions come from a combination of reduced glacier melt water (once glaciers shrink) and shifting monsoon patterns. Studies (e.g. Immerzeel et al., 2020) highlight that the Indus Basin is one of the most vulnerable basins in Asia, absent adaptive measures, water supply is expected to become highly unreliable: larger floods and longer dry spells.

Other than climate, water allocation conflicts are also driven by socio-economic factors. Water use is dominated by agriculture in both countries. To support staple crops and cotton, roughly 90% of the water consumption in Pakistan is agricultural. Irrigated agriculture is heavily favoured by the political economy of Pakistan, water intensive cropping (especially cotton) are controlled by powerful landowning elites and reforms for cropping shifts and equitable water pricing are resisted. Even when the supply falls, this locks Pakistan into high water demand.

Irrigation (rice-wheat rotation) is also prioritized by India’s Punjab and Jammu regions, but India has major hydropower investment and a more diversified use of water. Both Countries continue to urbanize and industrialize; their growing economies and population (Pakistan 250 million, India 1.4 billion) have increased the industrial and municipal demand of water. Institutional and governance factors do matter on the inside. The outdated laws (Colonial-era Canal and Drainage Act), intra-provincial disputes (Sindh vs Punjab), and poor efficiency in irrigation have made Pakistan’s water sector suffer a lot. This means that social tension is fueled within Pakistan as not all communities get sufficient water. The interstate water sharing in India (between Jammu and Punjab) is also controversial, and uncertainty is fueled by lack of unified management and robust data sharing. Manto (2023) observes that water insecurity in Pakistan is brought up by its political economy “unequal access to clean water” and powerful agricultural lobbies, therefore governance weaknesses and political interests also affect allocations, and not only the socio-economic driver (demand growth).

RESEARCH METHODS

A qualitative research approach is used in this study, with essentials of comparative case analysis. The focus is not to quantify the variables, but to understand the complexity of relationships. A descriptive research design is followed, in which, under the Environmental Security Theory, the data of environmental science is incorporated with international relations analysis. Fundamentally, it is a case study of the Indus Basin with comparative references to other river basins. Exclusively the secondary sources were used for the collection of data, which include books, reports from international organizations (IPCC, UN, World Bank), journal articles, think tank analyses, treaty documents, news media (BBC, Reuters), and historical sources. Primarily, content analysis was conducted, and different themes (climate change impacts, treaty issues, and conflict incidents) were studied and identified, and to ensure robustness the sources were triangulated. The Kishanganga dam dispute and India's 2025 suspension of the treaty were some notable cases which were examined, and major floods illustrated the dynamics of climate stress, treaty interaction and national security implication.

CLIMATE CHANGE AND WATER AVAILABILITY IN THE INDUS BASIN

In the Indus Basin, as increased water stress, climate change is already noticeable. As large portion of the flow of basin is derived from the melting of snow and glaciers, researchers declare that the reliability of this supply is reducing with climate driven changes. The glacial melt, varies by sub basin, but contributes over one-third of Indus discharge (Giese et al. 2022). Researchers warn that base flow will shrink over time due to accelerated glacial loss. Estimatedly, glacial melt and snow, contributes to 72% of rivers overflow. Therefore, any decrease in winter/spring snowpack or glacial mass has huge impact. Certainly, over the past five decades, data has shown a considerable retreat of lower elevation glaciers in Karakoram and Himalayas. These changes are reflected in observed trends. A 5% decrease in the overall Indus flow is indicated in the observational records (1962-2024). The decline is predominant in post-monsoon (Oct-Dec) because of snowmelt and monsoon. The extreme events are also mounting at the same time

as record breaking floods were experienced in 2010 and 2022 in the basin, which were caused by glacial outbursts and unusually heavy rainfall. The destabilizing potential of the climate variability can be seen in the massive destruction caused by these floods. The flows of irrigation have experienced reductions, as heat waves (2015 and 2017) have brought severe drought like conditions and played equally. So, water variability, both shortages and floods has increased.

Overall Indus water availability is reducing due to climate change and it increases uncertainty. South Asia is highly vulnerable to such changes, its population and irrigated agriculture, warned by the scientists. The stakes of water dispute are high, as there will be fewer buffers for sharing, even with minor flow reductions. Pakistan will face disproportional challenges, if the flows decline systematically as the allocations were based on mid 20th century flow data, being the lower riparian. The Think Tank Journal analysis observes that the river's flow will be significantly reduced due to reduction in glacial melt because of rising temperatures, worsening water scarcity in both Pakistan and India.

SOCIO-ECONOMIC DRIVERS OF ALLOCATION AND DEMAND

Socio-economic factors are increasing the demand, while climate change tightens the supply. A large growing population of around 300 million is supported by the Indus Basin, and it is expected to exceed 380 million by 2050. In Pakistan (250 million), over the recent decades, the average per capita water availability has dropped. Municipal and factory water use is increased due to urbanization and industrialization, but still, agriculture remains the largest demand. The agriculture in Pakistan is greatly water intensive, water hungry crops like cotton and rice, farming utilize about 90% of the water. Social unrest is expected if any cuts are observed due to powerful political backing in these sectors. The reforms (crop diversification, pricing) that could ease shortages, are blocked by the Pakistan's elite interests tied to water intensive agriculture, noted by the analysts. Climate stress is magnified by the socio-political inertia. Similarly, the regions of Punjab and Jammu & Kashmir in India rely on Indus tributaries. India has gradually increased withdrawals from the treaty allocated eastern rivers, due to its agricultural expansion (wheat,

rice). Waters can be shared indirectly (Indira and Bhakra canals) even though India controls eastern rivers. Dam construction is also derived from India's quest for electricity. India's five-year plans include growing hydro capacity in Kashmir (e.g. Kishanganga), which it funds through state-owned companies. Therefore, in both Pakistan and India the basin demand is rose by their development goals.

Socio-economic interests is what shapes water allocation, population need water to drink, states pursue energy independence, and powerful agriculture lobbies demand high irrigation. There are deep rooted and growing demands. BBC analysis said, that a severe reduction in the flow of Indus Basin (engineered or climate induced) would be destructive for Pakistan's economy (crop failures, flooding farmland with salinity), as 80% of farming in Pakistan depend on Indus waters. Think Tank Journal also warns that food shortages, increased poverty, and loss of livelihoods may be experienced if flow is reduced, and could devastate Pakistan's agriculture. Water scarcity poses some serious threats directly to social stability and human security in both countries. The political cost of reallocating water (away from sindh or rising prices for farmers) is great. Hence, not only that pressure is increased on water resources but compromise is also made difficult due to socioeconomic factors

SHORTCOMINGS OF THE INDUS WATERS TREATY UNDER CLIMATE STRESS

The Indus Waters Treaty is operational and functioning from decades, but many analysts have argued that in the contemporary context the IWT has significant gaps in it, which include:

- **Lack of climate resilience provisions:** The IWT's text makes no mention of climate change, glacial melt variability, or extreme events. Its design is for predictable flows, and many argue that the effect of climate change on overall water availability and regional distribution beyond national level are not considered in this treaty. Meaning that if the flow declines, there is no mechanism to renegotiate. The fixed allocation percentages would become unreliable as the flow shrinks.
- **Storage and infrastructure limits:** Observers note that Pakistan rely on seasonal flow and has few large reservoirs based on treaty design and hence IWT limits possibilities for storage on

the western rivers. India on the other hand has freedom to build run of river projects (restricted in dam height & size) on western rivers. On which Pakistan says that it could cumulatively reduce the flow. Without a limit on the number of Indian dams, there is a loophole in the treaty. Storage (reservoirs) can buffer variability in a warming climate. Treaty's limitations hinder this adaptation.

- **No quantitative sharing beyond baseline:** The IWT simply awards whole rivers and it does not specify minimum flows or sharing beyond East-West, unlike some water treaties. There is an ambiguity that Pakistan would have to rely on arbitration if India builds projects that slows flows (within design rules). This will lead to disputes (such as in Baglihar and Kishanganga) as many experts warned. Real time monitoring is also weak as there is no transparency and also no joint data sharing clause beyond annual meetings.
- **Inflexible dispute resolution:** Neutral experts and arbitration is provided by World Bank as treaty entrusts the body as a neutral party. Though, in a crisis (sudden flow cut) the mechanism may not respond quickly, and the resolutions can be very slow (years for an award). Furthermore, after a recent terrorist attack that India falsely accuse Pakistan of, was an extralegal action that throws mechanism into uncertainty, as India's recent move to put in abeyance its participation in the treaty (2025) suggests that high politics still encroach. A lack of enforcement was seen after this incident indicating that either side could abandon the treaty under extreme pressure.
- **Outdated focus:** Climate change also results in salt water intrusion and pollution from floods, but the water quality and ground water in Indus aquifer (which Pakistan is over extracting) are the key modern concerns that are not addressed and sole focus of IWT is surface water. Efficiency (irrigation improvement) and demand management are also absent. In real, the treaty doesn't focuses on intergrated basin management, and rather does on engineered works, which makes it narrow. These shortcomings are potential for conflict. Given its lack of storage, Pakistan may perceive Indian projects as existential threats under drought conditions. On the other hand, India lets Pakistan to cry foul and considers its projects legitimate under IWT rights. The environmental

stresses are left to political negotiations because of treaty's silence on it and eventually it can cause conflict because of mistrust. The shortcomings thus undermine cooperation and increase the chance of unilateral action. As one analysis notes, the treaty "limits possibilities for storage" and "does not promote collaborative development of the basin". In the climate-change context, many experts call the IWT outdated and in need have overhaul.

HYDRO-POLITICAL TENSIONS AND CASE STUDIES

Several recent cases illustrate how water tensions play out in practice. We highlight three: Kishanganga dam, 2016 Uri-Kashmir crisis, and the 2025 treaty suspension.

- **Kishanganga Hydroelectric Project** (India's dispute): The Kishanganga (Neelum) project in Indian-administered Kashmir diverts the Neelum River (a tributary of the Jhelum) through a tunnel to feed a power plant. Pakistan objected that this would reduce Neelum River flow into Pakistan. The IWT did not explicitly forbid such diversion, but limits flow reduction. In 2013, the World Bank tribunal allowed India to proceed but ordered minimum flows (9 cubic meters per sec) to Pakistan. This episode showed the treaty's arbitration working, but only after years. The changing glacial melt patterns have cited by both sides. Though climate context is not considered by international arbitration, Pakistan argues that the ruling should have been altered by the ruling. The example of how, when legal clarity is lacking, disputes over hydropower can escalate interstate tensions.

- **Uri Attack and IWT Chill (2016)**: "Blood and water cannot flow together", Indian PM Modi famously said after a militant attack in Uri sector in Kashmir, mentioning a possible withdrawal from the treaty. Water had become part of the security narrative as can be seen in this symbolic linking of terrorism and water rights. India temporarily delayed World Bank-IWT proceedings instead of formally revoking the treaty. This case demonstrates that water can be used as a bargaining chip in security events. Pakistan wrote to India on it that any stop to Indus flow is "act of war", as it was a crisis for Pakistan. The case raised in international media, concerning the treaty's durability under political stress. It demonstrates that under extreme

political events or intense time, water can be used as a weapon, though it doesn't revolve around climate.

- **India's 2025 Treaty Suspension**: India, following an April terror attack (blamed on Pakistan), put in abeyance the IWT in May 2025, reported by Reuters. Via an old canal India announced that it would divert more water from Chenab, which will reduce the flow to Pakistan and experts warn that it would severely affect the irrigation of Pakistan, if fully implemented. Reports say that Pakistan was prepared for such projects as these would take years, as at one intake there is already a temporary 90% drop caused by maintenance by India in May 2025. So, water stress can be escalated immediately by unilateral political decisions (suspending treaty obligations). Any further cut can be crucial as both countries are under drought stress lately. The environmental resources have become tied to national interests as Indian Water Ministry said "not a drop of water goes out".

CLIMATE CHANGE AS A CONFLICT CATALYST

Noting the things mentioned above, putting them all together we can now analyze that how water dispute is intensified by climate stress.

- **Reduced buffers and heightened stakes**: A bigger relative shortage is caused by any reduction in flow due to withdrawal or any water project, for instance now a downstream might be left dry because of a diversion while it could have been managed under earlier flow levels. Pakistan tolerance is very low for reduced inflow as 80% of farming in Pakistan depends on Indus. Pakistan was alarmed by even a routine maintenance by India (90% drop at one intake). Mutual distrust is caused by such incidents, and the spare water is effectively reduced in the system by climate change, and will make intentional diversions or even accidental slippages more anxious.

- **Changes in demand timing**: Misjudgement in allocation could be a possibility if the reservoirs fill too late or too early, because of earlier melting caused by warmer springs, shifting irrigation demand. Pakistan could be deprived of its share during critical times if India uses more headwater early, anticipating flows that now occur later, so these timing shifts can cause conflicts if not scheduled adaptively.

- **Extreme events and blame:** Floods and droughts are carried by climate change along with it and Pakistan could blame India if any severe drought is witnessed and flow is further reduced by an infrastructure. On the other hand India might blame Pakistan if downstream damage is caused by upstream flow. As, India is being blamed by Pakistan that without any warning the flood waters are released. As countries compete for declining resources so, changing precipitation and melt patterns can heighten tensions. So, climate impacts fuel political narratives (“India is stealing our water”).
- **Legal and institutional inflexibility:** Many commentators call for updating the IWT as it is ill equipped to handle new variables and has no method to renegotiate allocations under changing conditions. The Think Tank Journal suggests modifying the treaty to account for climate change, improved data sharing, and mediation mechanisms. Similarly, climate-diplomacy analysis concludes that meeting this challenge requires “arrangements to take pre-emptive action against natural disasters such as flooding or drought”. So far, neither side has formally attempted a treaty revision, partly due to mistrust. This institutional lag means every climate shock is handled ad hoc, raising conflict risk.
- **Environmental security intersection:** Interpreted through Environmental Security Theory, the Indus case confirms its propositions. Climate stress (environmental scarcity) interacts with existing political fault lines (India-Pak rivalry, Kashmir conflict) to produce a volatile mix. Scholars (e.g. Eckersley) argue such ecological factors become “catalysts” for conflict if they meet governance deficiencies. Indeed, Pakistan’s government now routinely frames its relations with India in terms of water security, and even Pakistan’s judiciary has considered the treaty’s fate. India’s suspension of treaty obligations in 2025 demonstrates a securitization of water (using national security pretexts to justify water policy changes).

FINDINGS

This study finds that the Pakistan-India water dispute is increasingly becoming an **environmental security** issue under climate change. The key findings are:

- **Climate Impacts Are Significant:** The Indus Basin’s water supply is highly climate-

sensitive. Over 30-40% of flow derives from glacial and snow melts. Flow is reduced (5% 1962-2014) and droughts and floods can be seen already because of warming. Indus basin is rated highly vulnerable to climate, and if greenhouse emission remains high the river flow will reduce substantially.

- **Socio-Economic Pressures Are Growing:** Pakistan and India both have huge populations and economies that increase water demand. Most of water in Pakistan is utilized by elite driven agriculture (cotton, rice). Dam construction and irrigation expansion is driven by India’s agriculture and energy ambitions. So, pressure is on water allocations due to these factors.

- **Indus Waters Treaty Limitations:** Lack of provisions to handle modern realities is seen in the IWT which was a remarkable achievement in its time. It doesn’t contain any renegotiation mechanism and place a limit on storage and joint management. Critics argue that it only addresses surface flows and ignore climate change effects, it does not promote collaborative development. This means that political means are used to deal with these climate or demand shocks rather than agreed process.

- **Environmental Security Risks Are Rising:** Climate change is a “Threat Multiplier”. Tensions are amplified when water stress met the long standing Kashmir issue. The issue of water is now a national security problem to be spoken off, for instance India’s suspension of the treaty and dam projects. Reducing the water share of the other is what both Pakistan and India think is a strategic goal. These developments explain that resource stresses can intensify geopolitical rivalries (Environmental Security Theory).

Resilience factors are which must not be ignored despite the challenges and both Pakistan and India have incentives to prevent the conflict and have continued communication via different channels like the Indus Commission. If water is used cooperatively it can also create opportunities for confidence building, for instance, mistrust can be reduced by data sharing and joint water management. Environmental factors to be integrated into diplomacy can lead to long term peace in the region.

CONCLUSION

A broader Truth of our time, security concerns are linked with environmental changes, is revealed

by the Indus Basin dispute. The limits are IWT are now put to test by the climate change, as this treaty has prevented war over water for over six decades. This Paper has shown that as socio-economic drivers are intensifying the competition, the water availability in the basin is reduced by climate change. These stresses could lead to conflict if not modified. Such ecological stressors worsen the existing rivalries as suggested by Environmental Security Theory. Recent events confirmed that in Pakistan and India water has intertwined with national security.

Though, a way forward is also suggested that both Pakistan and India can achieve environmental security and can mitigate conflict if they update institutions accordingly and recognize water as a shared resource. Recommendations will include improving the governance, making treaty reforms, and joint adaptation planning, which will ensure water as a bridge rather than a barrier.

Lastly, sustainable water management under climate change will ensure true security in the region. Indus Basin could again become an example of “water for peace” if Pakistan and India can translate environmental imperatives into cooperative action, with a modern framework that suits the climate era. On the other hand, tension will be added to the already serious risk facing South Asia if adaptation is ignored, and its urgency can be observed as one think tank analysis warns that the pressures of climate change are being increasingly tested. The choices we made today will shape the region’s security for decades to come.

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